

Trade liberalization by less developed countries with a large market size: Meager welfare gains?

Adolfo Cristóbal Campoamor

Department of Economics, University of Alcalá, Madrid, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

JEL classification:

F41
F32

Keywords:

Trade liberalization
North-south convergence
Market size
Comparative advantage

ABSTRACT

In this paper we present a one-sector Dixit-Stiglitz-Krugman model of North-South trade, in order to evaluate the welfare and convergence implications of a gradual, bilateral trade liberalization. Using the same formal setting that generated the “new trade theory” wave, we show that a technologically disadvantaged South may diverge in welfare terms with the North, provided that its population and market size were large enough. Both countries are shown to benefit from trade in absolute terms. The causality mechanism deals with a home-market effect, which reinforces the potential exports of the largest economy, and a simultaneous terms-of-trade effect, which preserves trade balance by reducing the relative prices and wage rate of the largest and poorest country.

1. Introduction

Paul Krugman popularized a major research line in which scale economies and imperfect competition were the main modelling features that allowed for gains from international trade, even in the absence of comparative advantage at the country level. Later on, multiple articles on “new trade theory” and “new economic geography” have addressed the welfare and convergence effects of higher trade freeness (e.g., Das (2005), Charlot et al. (2006), Behrens et al. (2007)...). Broadly speaking, the conclusions on welfare seem to be strongly assumption-and-model dependent: sometimes welfare benefits from trade come after its costs; other times regional inequalities initially rise to eventually fall; sometimes disparities evolve in a monotonic fashion. Here we have explored the original modelling source of the literature, based on the one-sector Dixit-Stiglitz-Krugman model, to study analytically some implications of *gradual* trade liberalization.

According to Krugman (1979), when we consider a one-sector economy under a monopolistically competitive market structure, a comparison between autarky and fully open trade always yields welfare benefits for all parties. Under a positive level of trade costs (see e.g., Krugman (1980)) the country with the largest market will be more prosperous in terms of real wages, via a home-market effect. And all welfare differences between (technologically symmetric) countries will naturally disappear in the absence of trade costs. These findings suggest that a progressive trade liberalization will yield gradual convergence in terms of real wages. This convergence presumption has been often

characterized as a “market size effect”.

Our purpose in the present piece is to prove that his conclusions in terms of welfare still hold when we contemplate a gradual decay in trade costs, regardless of the initial level of trade freeness. Furthermore, we will simultaneously incorporate to the analysis some technological asymmetries between countries. Consequently, we conclude that countries with a sizeable enough market, due to a large labor force, but lower levels of productivity and wellbeing, will experience divergence and limited gains from barely liberalizing trade. To the extent that they had better take further advantage of parallel opportunities offered by globalization, like the diffusion of ideas and the international relocation of production (see e.g., Baldwin (2016)).

This paper is related to the findings presented by Felbermayr and Jung (2015)’s working paper, in the context of a model with heterogeneous firms and selection. They endogenized the Southern productivity disadvantages, although the complexity of their setting prevented them from obtaining clear, closed-form conditions for North-South divergence, in terms of the parameters.

2. Main features of a well-known model

The economy represented by the model consists of two countries: South (S) and North (N). Their local populations (L_S and L_N) work in a single manufacturing sector and receive wages w_S and w_N , respectively. Let us denote by n_S (n_N), p_S (p_N) and x_S (x_N) the existing number of product varieties, their prices and their individual output levels in

E-mail address: adolfo.cristobal@uah.es.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2025.112240>

Received 21 October 2024; Received in revised form 2 February 2025; Accepted 15 February 2025

Available online 17 February 2025

0165-1765/© 2025 The Author. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

country S (N). Therefore, a trade balance condition requires that the local aggregate income be equal to the revenue obtained by local firms in both countries:

$$w_S L_S = n_S p_S x_S; \quad w_N L_N = n_N p_N x_N \quad (1)$$

Preferences and technology are characterized by the well-known Dixit-Stiglitz monopolistically competitive setting, with a CES utility function over manufacturing varieties and increasing returns to scale in production. In particular, let us denote by φ_S^{-1} and φ_N^{-1} the country-specific level of fixed costs and the constant marginal cost in terms of labor, respectively, exhibited by firms in country S (N). φ_k , $k \in \{S, N\}$ is in this case a measure of both the productivity of local firms and the institutional facility to enter the product markets and do business.

On the demand side, the elasticity of substitution between product varieties will be denoted by σ (> 1). Therefore, given the available technology in each country we can already advance as follows the labor market-clearing conditions:

$$L_S = n_S (\varphi_S^{-1} + m x_S); \quad L_N = n_N (\varphi_N^{-1} + m x_N) \quad (2)$$

Since the firm's pricing decision determines a constant markup over marginal costs, necessarily

$$p_k = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma - 1} m w_k; \quad k \in \{S, N\}$$

where we have normalized $m \equiv \frac{\sigma - 1}{\sigma}$, and then $p_k = w_k$. Given the assumption of free entry into the product markets and the above-mentioned existence of fixed costs, the corresponding zero-profit-condition determines de equilibrium output per firm in each country k (x_k). If we denote by π_k the profits net of fixed costs,

$$\pi_k = \frac{m w_k}{\sigma - 1} x_k - \varphi_k^{-1} w_k = 0, \quad \text{i.e.} \quad x_k = \sigma \varphi_k^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, from (2) and (3),

$$n_k = \frac{\varphi_k L_k}{\sigma}; \quad \text{i.e.} \quad L_k = n_k x_k; \quad k \in \{S, N\} \quad (4)$$

The measures of active manufacturing firms then depend positively on the population size of the country and its productivity level. Now we can use the fact that, by (3) and (4),

$$L_S = n_S x_S = \frac{w_S L_S (w_S^{-\sigma})}{w_S^{1-\sigma} + \delta \frac{n_N}{n_S}} + \frac{\delta w_N L_N (w_S^{-\sigma})}{\delta w_S^{1-\sigma} + \frac{n_N}{n_S}} \quad (5)$$

where $\delta \equiv \tau^{1-\sigma}$ ($0 < \delta < 1$) is the usual indicator of trade freeness and $\tau > 1$ stands for the iceberg trade cost between North and South. The right-hand side of (5) captures the aggregate demand for all the varieties produced in S , coming from both country S and country N . Moreover, let us define $\omega \equiv \frac{w_S}{w_N}$, $\theta \equiv \frac{L_S}{L_S + L_N}$ and $d \equiv \frac{n_S}{n_S + n_N} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\varphi_N(1-\theta)}{\varphi_S \theta}}$. It is possible then to rewrite the last expression in (5) as

$$L_S = \frac{L_S}{1 + \frac{\delta}{s}} + \frac{\frac{L_N}{\omega}}{\delta + \frac{1}{s}}, \quad \text{where} \quad s \equiv \frac{d}{1-d} \omega^{1-\sigma} \quad (6)$$

And then, solving implicitly for ω , we can find that,

$$\omega = \frac{1-\theta}{\theta} \left(\frac{s(s+\delta)}{1+\delta s} \right) \quad (7)$$

In order to obtain an implicit characterization of the variable s , it is possible to manipulate (6) and (7) and derive that,

$$s^\sigma \left(\frac{s+\delta}{1+\delta s} \right)^{\sigma-1} = \frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \right)^\sigma \quad (8)$$

It is important to provide now an economic interpretation of the endogenous variable s . To that purpose, let us denote by s' the ratio between the Southern and the Northern aggregate incomes. After rearranging in (7),

$$s' \equiv \frac{w_S L_S}{w_N L_N} = \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \omega = \frac{s(\delta+s)}{1+\delta s} \quad (9)$$

That is, under conditions of perfectly free trade ($\delta \approx 1$), $s' = s$, and s becomes an indicator of the local market size of country S relative to country N . However, there is still another interpretation of s that holds for any value of trade freeness. Let us denote by x_N^{exp} and x_N^{dom} the sales by any Northern firm to the foreign and to the domestic market, respectively. Then, it is straightforward to show that, using (7),

$$\frac{x_N^{exp}}{x_N^{dom}} = \frac{\delta w_S L_S}{w_N L_N} \left(\frac{\delta n_S w_S^{1-\sigma} + n_N w_N^{1-\sigma}}{n_S w_S^{1-\sigma} + \delta n_N w_N^{1-\sigma}} \right) = \delta \omega \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \left(\frac{1+\delta s}{\delta+s} \right) = \delta s \quad (10)$$

Therefore,

$$s = \frac{x_N^{exp}}{\delta x_N^{dom}} \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) means that, if the domestic sales are especially abundant (small) for any Northern firm relative to the exports, the endogenous variable s will tend to have a low (high) value. At this point, the following auxiliary Lemma 1 will be necessary to obtain our conditions for nominal and real convergence between South and North.

Lemma 1. *The expression (8) above characterizes implicitly the variable s as a function of all the exogenous parameters in our model (φ_S , φ_N , θ , σ , δ). It is possible to derive that $s < (>) 1$ if and only if $\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \right)^\sigma < (>) 1$, regardless of the level of δ .*

Proof: See the Appendix.

The previous Lemma 1 implies that the market size in S will be larger than N 's if, under increasing returns to scale, the Southern population (represented by θ) is sufficiently large; the Southern technological disadvantage ($\frac{\varphi_N}{\varphi_S}$) is not too important; and the elasticity of substitution (σ) is high enough. Under these conditions, Southern firms will enjoy from a competitive advantage that results from the relative scale of their country's population; the possibility of rapid firm entry in response to higher demand; and the channeling of Northern imports toward their varieties. As a result, Southern firms will exhibit a considerable demand for local labor, and will enlarge S 's wages and market size.

Some results to be presented below could be better understood if we pay attention now to an additional derivation. By combining (7) and (8) it is possible to get that

$$s^{1-m} \omega^m = \bar{K}^{1-m} \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{K} \equiv \frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \right)$ and $m \equiv \frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma} < 1$.

Expression (12) reveals that, given constant technological and demographic conditions, if trade liberalization raised s then the Southern relative wage ω would fall. If we look at the characterization of s in (11), our intuition can develop a bit further: a higher value of s means (for a Northern firm) fewer domestic sales in the North and more exports to the South, since $x_N^{exp} + x_N^{dom} = x_N = \sigma \varphi_N^{-1}$ is constant. Therefore, that will only hold if N 's relative prices increase, i.e., if ω falls.

3. Conditions for trade-induced convergence and divergence

Since we have already solved implicitly for the nominal, relative wage ω in expressions (6) and (7), it is now possible to analyze the conditions for convergence in welfare levels as a result of a gradual trade liberalization.

Let us denote by $\omega_R \equiv \omega \frac{L_S}{L_N}$ the relative welfare level, i.e., the relative real wage, of country S relative to country N . The endogenous variables I_S and I_N refer to the relevant price indices in S and N , respectively. Firstly, we will restate the ratio of both price indices in terms of the relative market size (s) and our level of trade freeness (δ) as follows:

$$\frac{I_N}{I_S} = \left(\frac{n_S w_S^{1-\sigma} + \delta n_N w_N^{1-\sigma}}{\delta n_S w_S^{1-\sigma} + n_N w_N^{1-\sigma}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\sigma-1}} = \left(\frac{s + \delta}{1 + \delta s} \right)^{\frac{1}{\sigma-1}} \quad (13)$$

Then, combining the Eqs. (6), (7) and (13) above, we can conclude that $s < 1$ is both necessary and sufficient condition for the Southern relative wage (ω) and relative welfare level (ω_R) to increase. However, our market size s is an endogenous variable, so we need to use the previous Lemma 1 to establish the following result in terms of the parameters:

Proposition 1. *A necessary and sufficient condition for both ω and ω_R to rise with a gradual trade liberalization, regardless of the initial level of δ , is:*

$$\theta < \frac{\left(\frac{\varphi_N}{\varphi_S} \right)^{\frac{1}{\sigma}}}{1 + \left(\frac{\varphi_N}{\varphi_S} \right)^{\frac{1}{\sigma}}} \quad (14)$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

It is possible to observe in (14) that, in the case of symmetric technologies in both countries ($\varphi_S = \varphi_N$), convergence will be the rule, since the smaller and poorer country (e.g., the South if $\theta < \frac{1}{2}$) will gain in relative terms from trade liberalization. However, the possibility of differentiated technologies opens the way to new phenomena, which will allow for international divergence as will be emphasized in Section 5.

Here a home-market effect favors the expansion of the country with the largest initial market size, i.e. s will rise (fall) with trade liberalization if it was originally higher (lower) than one. Nevertheless, such expansion in the largest market will give rise, due to the trade-balance conditions, to a terms-of-trade effect: to preserve the balance of external accounts, the relative prices of the largest national market must decay. And so will the relative wage of the largest economy, both in nominal and real terms. Finally, this terms-of-trade effect fully determines the patterns of international convergence.

4. Welfare analysis

In order to analyze the effect of gradual trade liberalization on the representative welfare levels in countries S and N , first we need to express the local real wages in terms of the relative market size (s) and the parameters of the model. In particular, if we denote by V_k the welfare level in country k ,

$$V_S = \frac{w_S}{I_S} = \frac{w_S}{(n_S w_S^{1-\sigma} + \delta n_N w_N^{1-\sigma})^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma}}}; \quad V_N = \frac{w_N}{I_N} = \frac{w_N}{(\delta n_S w_S^{1-\sigma} + n_N w_N^{1-\sigma})^{\frac{1}{1-\sigma}}} \quad (15)$$

By applying our previous definitions of d and s to (15), it is possible to produce the following expressions for both local welfare levels:

$$V_S = \left[\frac{\varphi_S L_S (\delta + s)}{\sigma s} \right]^{\frac{1}{\sigma-1}}; \quad V_N = \left[\frac{\varphi_N L_N (1 + \delta s)}{\sigma} \right]^{\frac{1}{\sigma-1}} \quad (16)$$

From (7), (8) and (16) it is also possible to derive the following Lemma 2, which will become an essential ingredient for our final conclusions.

Lemma 2. *When trade tends to become perfectly free (i.e. when $\delta \rightarrow 1^-$), V_S will be lower (higher) than V_N , if and only if $\varphi_S < (>) \varphi_N$.*

Proof: See the Appendix.

The meaning of this lemma is intuitive enough: when trade freeness is almost complete, there is hardly any difference between local market sizes and the welfare levels are uniquely determined by technological efficiency.

Proposition 2. *A marginal rise in trade freeness unambiguously increases*

the welfare levels in S and N , regardless of the initial level of trade costs.

Proof: See the Appendix.

Krugman (1979) presented two potential sources of gains from trade: a competitive reduction in markups and an expansion in product variety. He compared autarky with perfectly free trade. However, neither of these two reasons for higher welfare levels appear in our model, which exhibits a gradual decrease in trade costs: the world mass of varieties stays constant (see (4)) and so does the typical markup. Therefore, here cheaper imports work in favor of consumers from both countries, while the terms-of-trade effect positively (negatively) impacts the welfare levels in the smallest (largest) national economy. However, absolute welfare levels increase in both countries and relative welfare levels always evolve monotonically as δ rises.

5. Less developed countries with a large market size

It is true that a more realistic picture of a less developed economy (our country S) should contain a second productive sector, with a homogeneous primary good. However, the current modernization of vast and heavily populated areas of the world could make the conclusions from this one-sector model potentially relevant, at least in a forward-looking sense.

If our country S encompasses the largest market size due to its overwhelming population, although its well-being is scant due to the limits of its own technology or institutions, S would still gain from trade liberalization, though at a lower rate than country N . Our next Proposition 3 shows the conditions for divergence at the last stages of trade liberalization.

Proposition 3. *If trade freeness is sufficiently close to being perfect ($\delta \rightarrow 1^-$), the poorer country S will diverge with respect to N , by further liberalizing trade, if and only if*

$$\theta > \frac{\left(\frac{\varphi_N}{\varphi_S} \right)^{\frac{1}{\sigma}}}{1 + \left(\frac{\varphi_N}{\varphi_S} \right)^{\frac{1}{\sigma}}} > \frac{1}{2} \quad (17)$$

Or, equivalently, if

$$1 < \left(\frac{\varphi_N}{\varphi_S} \right) < \left(\frac{\theta}{1 - \theta} \right)^{\sigma} \quad (18)$$

Proof: Straightforward from Proposition 1 and Lemma 2.

The first inequality in (18) means that country S must be poorer than country N in terms of real wages, due to a technological disadvantage. The second inequality implies that, simultaneously, the productivity in S (although lower) must be high enough so that the South still owns the largest market. If both conditions are verified, then the terms-of-trade effect will work against the interest of the largest and most disfavored economy. Therefore, further trade liberalization will be followed by international divergence.

6. Conclusions

This paper tries to shed light, from a new trade theory perspective, on the welfare and convergence implications of bilateral trade reforms. To that purpose, we have chosen the simplest setting that gave rise to this novel research wave in the last four decades. And we have obtained insights that may have been overlooked, often in contrast to the implications of recent models. This fact suggests that the connection between trade and welfare is not yet settled, and requires further theoretical and empirical exploration. The results could be briefly summarized as follows:

If the Southern economy exhibits a technological or institutional disadvantage in the form of higher firm entry costs, and a much larger

population and market size, this model shows that the combination of a home-market and a terms-of-trade effect, after trade liberalization, may be detrimental to the convergence aspirations of the South.

APPENDIX

Proof of Lemma 1:

Throughout this appendix, we will denote by x_β the derivative of any variable x with respect to the parameter β .

The left-hand side of the Eq. (8) can be shown to be strictly increasing in s , for any given value of δ . Therefore, the equilibrium value of s is unique, given the continuity of the function and Bolzano’s theorem. If we totally differentiate the expression (8) above with respect to δ , we will finally get that,

$$\frac{s_\delta}{s} = \frac{-m(1 - s^2)}{\delta + (1 + m)s + (1 - m)s\delta^2 + \delta s^2} \tag{A.1}$$

where $m \equiv \frac{\sigma-1}{\sigma}$. Consequently, from (12) and (A.1),

$$\frac{\omega_\delta}{\omega} = \frac{(1 - m)(1 - s^2)}{\delta + (1 + m)s + (1 - m)s\delta^2 + \delta s^2} \tag{A.2}$$

Now let us assume that Lemma 1 does not hold and proceed to find contradictions.

There are two possible ways in which Lemma 1 may not be true: a) either $\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right)^\sigma > 1$ and $s \leq 1$, or b) $\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right)^\sigma < 1$ and $s \geq 1$. Let us find first a contradiction in a):

Given (A.1), if $s \leq 1$ we know that $s_\delta \leq 0$. Therefore, we will find a minimum value for s if $\delta = 1$, i.e., in that case $s_{min} = 1 < \frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right)^\sigma$ cannot be an equilibrium. Therefore, when $\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right)^\sigma > 1$ any equilibrium value of s cannot be lower or equal to one. And then a) cannot hold.

Let us find now a similar contradiction in b): If $s \geq 1$, then from (A.1) necessarily $s_\delta \geq 0$. Therefore, when $\delta = 1$ we will get a maximum value for s , which is exactly $s_{max} = 1 > \frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right)^\sigma$ and hence there are no equilibrium values for s that are higher or equal to one. Then b) does not hold either, which implies that Lemma 1 is true.

Proof of Proposition 1:

We already know from (A.2) that ω will be increasing in δ if and only if $s < 1$, i.e., if $\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right)^\sigma < 1$, according to Lemma 1. Let us consider now the conditions for ω_R to be increasing in δ as well.

First, we can derive from (16) that $\omega_R \equiv \frac{V_S}{V_N} = \left[\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right) \left(\frac{1+\frac{\delta}{s}}{1+\delta s}\right) \right]^{\frac{1}{\sigma-1}}$. Now by differentiating ω_R with respect to δ and after some algebra we can get that

$$\omega_{R,\delta} = \frac{s(1 - s)}{(1 + \delta)(s + \delta)} \left[1 - \delta + m\delta \left(\frac{1 + s^2 + 2\delta s}{s} \right) \left(\frac{1 + s}{\delta + (1 + m)s + (1 - m)s\delta^2 + \delta s^2} \right) \right] \tag{A.3}$$

where the final term in square brackets is strictly positive. Therefore, there will be North-South convergence in welfare terms only if $s < 1$, i.e., if

$$\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N} \left(\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}\right)^\sigma < 1 \tag{A.4}$$

The final expression in (14) results from restating (A.4) in terms of θ .

Proof of Lemma 2:

From (8) we can observe that, for values of δ sufficiently close to one, $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 1^-} s = \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} \left(\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N}\right)^{1/\sigma}$. Moreover, it is also possible to see from (7) and (8) that $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 1^-} \omega = \left(\frac{\varphi_S}{\varphi_N}\right)^{1/\sigma}$. Therefore, we can conclude that $\omega < 1$ if and only if $\varphi_S < \varphi_N$, provided that trade is sufficiently free. Exactly the same condition holds for real wages, since both price indices will become identical as $\delta \rightarrow 1^-$.

Proof of Proposition 2:

By totally differentiating V_S and V_N in (16) with respect to δ , it is possible to come up with a condition for a welfare gain in country S: $\frac{s_\delta}{s} < \frac{1}{\delta}$. Another condition for welfare gains in country N is $\frac{s_\delta}{s} > -\frac{1}{\delta}$. Finally, after some algebra, it is possible to conclude from (A.1) that both conditions necessarily hold ($-\frac{1}{\delta} < \frac{s_\delta}{s} < \frac{1}{\delta}$), implying that both countries always benefit from freer trade for any value of δ .

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

Baldwin, R., 2016. *The Great Convergence. Information Technology and the New Globalization*. Harvard University Press.

- Behrens, K., Gaigne, C., Ottaviano, G., Thisse, J.F., 2007. Countries, regions and trade: on the welfare impacts of economic integration. *Eur. Econ. Rev.* 51 (5), 1277–1301. July.
- Charlot, S., Gaigne, C., Robert-Nicoud, F., Thisse, J.F., 2006. Agglomeration and welfare: the core-periphery model in the light of Bentham, Kaldor and Rawls. *J. Public Econ.* 90 (1–2), 325–347. January.
- Das, S., 2005. Gradual globalization and inequality between and within countries. *Canad. Econ. Rev.* 38 (3), 852–869.
- Felbermayr, G., Jung, B., 2015. Market size and TFP in new, new trade theory. CESifo Working Paper No. 5583.
- Krugman, P., 1979. Increasing returns, monopolistic competition and international trade. *J. Int. Econ.* 9 (4), 469–479.
- Krugman, P., 1980. Scale economies, product differentiation and the pattern of trade. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 70 (5), 950–959.